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DESIGNING AND ANALYZING OPEN APPLICATION-ORIENTED LABS IN SOFTWARE-VERIFICATION EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The daily work of a software engineer frequently includes the design and implementation of systems in non-software-engineering disciplines, like medical technology, often in interdisciplinary teams. In order to successfully select and apply the appropriate theoretical concept to perform the task, it is necessary to understand the actual problem, possibly outside one's personal subject area, and to find an appropriate abstraction. However, software-engineering education often focuses on the theoretical concepts alone, ignoring the necessary skills to solve interdisciplinary tasks. We argue that the use of open, application-oriented labs creates a synergetic effect

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in understanding of theoretical concepts and the ability to apply them to solve practical issues. The subject of this study is a lab in the master's program module "Software Verification" at a German university of technology. Therein, student groups solve openly-formulated, application-oriented modeling tasks in the field of medical technology. In this paper, we present the design and an analysis of this lab by means of a student questionnaire after completion of the lab and a document analysis of 32 laboratory reports. Our survey results show that more than 90 % of the respondents state that the practical labs helped them to understand the theoretical content of the lectures. The evaluation of the lab reports shows that around half of the student groups were able to understand, abstract, and model the task correctly. We conclude that the inclusion of open, application-oriented labs in software-engineering education is beneficial to both, understanding of theoretical concepts and ability to solve interdisciplinary tasks.

1 INTRODUCTION

Digitalization brings software into more and more areas of our lives. Many of these areas are outside of computer science, where software enables other systems or processes to fulfill their tasks. These systems are built by interdisciplinary teams and require shared knowledge of the application domain [1]. In this work, we focus on the verification part of software development. The challenge in this context is to model the system at a working level of abstraction [2], formally specify the requirements, and then check the model against the specification using an appropriate algorithm. Fig. 1 shows the general workflow of complex, interdisciplinary problem solving in the area of computer science.

Fig. 1. Workflow of solving interdisciplinary issues

Preparing students for these tasks is a challenge for traditional software-engineering education. In traditional exercises, the students have to apply concepts learned in the lecture, but usually these pen-and-paper tasks are overly simple and already state which technique to apply. The students never have to consider which modeling formalism to choose or whether a detail should be included in the model or not. To overcome this limitation, we introduce open, application-oriented labs. These labs require the students to solve authentic and complex problems [3] based on an ongoing research project in the field of medical technology, providing an interdisciplinary, real-world scenario. Although the required medical knowledge is simplified and already provided in the task description, the tasks foster the competence to quickly extract the required medical and mechanical knowledge. The students must understand the problem, choose one of multiple possible ways to solve it, and deal with some uncertainties. The open, application-oriented labs put an emphasis on engaging students in research and inquiry [4], providing moderately ill-structured and moderately multi-disciplinary projects as proposed for undergraduate tasks in complex problem solving [5]. Furthermore, these labs better align the teaching activities with the learning goals of the course [6], which include the competences to develop models, to select appropriate verification techniques, and being able to identify and formulate new problems in the field of software verification.

In addition to being a necessity for software verification, abstraction is a key skill for computer science in general. Students who are able to abstract are also able to handle complexity and to produce elegant models and designs, but students who lack the ability to abstract struggle with complexity and the identification of the important parts of a problem [7].

In this work, we address the questions whether open, application-oriented labs help students 1) to better understand the key concepts presented in the lecture, 2) to abstract the actual problem of open interdisciplinary problems, and 3) to apply the taught concepts to solve these problems. The context of our study is a course on software verification at a German university of technology. The remainder of this article is structured as follows: In section 2, we provide some background on the software-verification course and introduce the open application-oriented tasks. In section 3, we present our evaluation methodology, and the results are presented in section 4. Section 5 contains a discussion of the results before section 6 concludes.

2 COURSE DESIGN OF SOFTWARE VERIFICATION

In this section, we provide some background on the course and the newly introduced open application-oriented labs.

2.1 Course Organization

The course “Software Verification” is a partly mandatory, partly elective module in four master’s programs. While most of the students take it in the first, a few take it in the third semester.

After completing the course, students should, among others, know the major verification techniques. They should be able to formalize and solve verification problems

and to justify their work. Additionally, they should be able to conduct independent research and to present their results.

The course “Software Verification” runs for fourteen weeks. It consists of a weekly lecture, which covers the theoretical concepts and logical foundations [8, 9], and is accompanied by a weekly recitation section. The recitation sections consist of *lab sessions* to get familiar with the tools, *group works* to work on verification projects using the introduced tools, *question sessions* to ask questions concerning the lecture and verification projects, and *presentation sessions* to present the results of verification projects. Therein, students deepen their understanding in six traditional exercise sheets with pen-and-paper tasks and three new lab sheets designed as verification projects in groups called “open application-oriented labs.” This study focuses on lab 1. The modeling tasks of lab 1 should be solved with the tool UPPAAL [10]. The students submit the models together with a documentation and present their results to the other students. To pass the module software verification, the students have to pass the exam as well as to achieve at least five points in sum for the three labs. The lab achievements are awarded as bonus points to the exam results.

2.2 Open Application-Oriented Labs

The interdisciplinary tasks for the open application-orientated lab 1 were taken, with some simplifications, from a new interdisciplinary research project at the institute. It addresses the medical technology issue *needle steering* by using formal methods. Automated needle steering is a new attempt in medicine technology for minimally invasive procedures. A flexible needle delivers treatment to a specific target, which requires careful guidance of the needle. For lab 1, we derived an introductory exercise and five different modeling tasks from the complex process of needle steering. The application-oriented tasks include the following topics among others: deformation of tissue, needle divergence, and the distribution of treatments around a target. For each student group, the lab consists of the same introductory exercise and one of the five tasks. The introductory exercise provides a helpful basis, but is not a prerequisite for solving the tasks and offers a first modelling approach. We randomly assigned the tasks to the student groups. All tasks are comparable in terms of workload and require the implementation of a physical or mathematical law. All tasks consist of a short description of the application context, a hint of the physical/mathematical background, the main task, and an additional optional task (c.f. Fig. 1).

In the task design, we have deliberately chosen an open question formulation. In a research context, we are interested in new solution approaches and want to give free rein to the students’ creativity. We also want to impart the necessary skills to solve complex, interdisciplinary problems. In designing the open interdisciplinary task derived from current research activities, particular attention needs to be paid to leveling out complexity and students’ autonomy in engaging the students in research and inquiry [11].

3 COURSE EVALUATION

The application-oriented labs are a prototype of a new teaching approach. We integrated the complex, interdisciplinary elements into the course, and we are interested in evaluating how promising the new approach is. Our assumptions are that the application-oriented labs help students

1. to comprehend the key concepts of software verification lecture and
2. to understand the open interdisciplinary issue, to abstract the actual problem and to apply theoretical key concepts to solve it.

The two assumptions represent different perspectives on the challenge of dealing with interdisciplinary tasks. The first idea claims that the application-oriented tasks motivate students to engage with theoretical contents of the lecture so that they understand them. The second idea claims an inverse relationship: by applying lectured theoretical concepts to interdisciplinary problems, students learn to deal with open, interdisciplinary issues, which require to take a look into other research areas and a classification and definition of the actual problem.

3.1 Study Methodology

We used a mixed-methods approach to evaluate both assumptions: a student survey and a document analysis of 31 submitted lab reports.

The students of the module were asked to answer 17 questions concerning the lab via a self-designed online questionnaire, which was conducted after completing the presentations of the lab 1. The focus of the first 14 closed questions was the understanding and the level of difficulty of the open, application-oriented tasks, the understanding of theoretical contents by the labs, and the cooperation within the group. The possible responses were detected on a 4-point agreement scale (*strongly agree*, *agree* and *disagree*, *strongly disagree*). Three openly formulated questions asked for understanding of the theoretical contents of the lecture, difficulties, while processing the labs, and improvement suggestions. We opened the online survey for one month for all registered participants of the module. 20 students completed the questionnaire; thus, a quarter of the participants took part voluntarily. Their responses are part of the evaluation. Furthermore, we evaluated the 31 labs submissions. Our document analysis included the evaluation the 62 submitted models (31 on the introduction exercise and 31 on the application-oriented tasks) on their technical and content-related correctness and was done by one teacher of the course. We classified the submitted models in three categories *unsatisfactory (C)*, *satisfactory (B)*, and *more than satisfactory (A)* using unambiguous technical and physical criteria. On the technical side, we checked whether the basic concepts of the theory of timed games were applied in the modeling artifacts. We have rated the tasks with a technical *B* if the basic concepts were implemented. Else, the groups got a *C*. Did the students also model further, more complex theoretical concepts beyond the basics, we rated the task with technical *A*. On the content-related side, we checked the realization of the required physical/mathematical law. We rated the task with content-related *B* if the idea was implemented correctly. Else, the students groups got a *C*. Did

the students also complete the optional task correctly, we rated the task with a content-related *A*. Of the introduction exercise we only checked the technical correctness, as the students were not asked to implement a physical or mathematical law. To evaluate assumption 1, we used the results of the survey regarding the understanding of theoretical concepts by the labs and the technical analysis of the submissions. The survey represents a self-assessment of the students, while our technical analysis of the models shows to what extent the students understood the theoretical contents based on solving the application-oriented labs. To evaluate assumption 2, we used the results of the survey regarding the understanding of the open, application-oriented tasks and the technical and content-related analysis of the models of the main tasks. On the basis of the survey, it can be classified whether *the students perceived the difficulty to understand the tasks*. While the analysis of the models shows the ability of the students to solve interdisciplinary problems.

3.2 Results

This section presents the results of the evaluation regarding assumption 1 and assumption 2.

The evaluation of the survey (see Fig. 2) and the document analysis (see Fig. 3) with regard to hypothesis 1 shows: Statement 4 *The practical exercises in the lab helped me to understand the theoretical content of the lecture* and Statement 5 *Solving an application-oriented task makes me more interested in the underlying theory* were replied by the overwhelming majority of the respondents with *strongly agree/agree* and barely with *disagree/strongly disagree*. Replies to the open formulated question 16 *Which topics of the lecture are possibly easier to understand after solving the task?* were: timed automata, guards, invariants, deadlocks, urgent and committed stages, model checking, logics and specification of properties. All mentioned keywords correspond to relevant theoretical concepts of the lecture. The results of the analysis of the 31 submissions concerning the correct implementation of theoretical concepts, regardless the content-related implementation, are: The introduction exercise and main task were completed of only a few groups unsatisfactorily *C*, with majority satisfactorily *B*, and of some groups more than satisfactorily *A*.

The evaluation of the survey and the document analysis with regard to assumption 2 shows: Half of the respondents replied *disagree* to statement 3 *I could easily understand the given tasks*, while the other half *agreed/strongly agreed*. The statement 7 *It was easy to solve the task based on lecture and tutorial* was *agreed/strongly agreed* by more than half of the respondents, while slightly less than half *disagreed/strongly disagreed*. In reply to open formulated question 17 concerning *the difficulties in solving the task*, the respondents stated inter alia: "Understanding the task problem. It was vague" and "More information could be provided for each task so that assumptions can be avoided". The respondents also noted their difficulties with the tool UP-PAAL.

Compared to the technical analysis of the 31 submissions of the tasks, the content-related analysis turned out worse: The tasks were completed by only slightly more than half of the groups satisfactorily or more than satisfactorily. Overall, 16 groups

Fig. 2. Evaluation of the survey

fulfilled the task well in terms of content (content-related *A* or *B*) and applied the theoretical concepts correctly (technical *A* or *B*) as depicted in Fig. 4. In contrast, for 15 groups we rated either the technical, the content implementation, or both with a *C*. The content-related and technical evaluation is identical for 19 submissions (*AA*, *BB*, or *CC*). Furthermore, the analysis shows: None of the groups had completely diverging technical and content-related results, there is no combination of *A* and *C* in the overall evaluation of the submissions. In fact, the content-related parts correlate positively with technical parts: All groups

with content-related *B* or *A* have at least a technical *B*, and only for one submission, the technical part is rated higher (with *A*) than the content-related part (with *B*). Further interesting findings of the survey are, that the overwhelming majority of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed with statement 6 *I enjoy solving the task* and statement 11 *I would appreciate to take more application-oriented tasks in the course*. The students' suggestions for improvement (question 18) were mainly related to the organizational realization of the labs. One student even replied explicitly: "Overall the labs were very good."

Fig. 3. Detailed Evaluation of lab submissions

Fig. 4. Evaluation of application-oriented labs submissions classified according to their technical and content evaluation

3.3 Discussion

The self-assessment of the respondents as well as the analysis of models regarding the application of theoretical concepts confirm hypothesis 1: The application-oriented

labs help students to understand the key concepts of the software verification lecture. The number of unsatisfactory submissions of the main tasks is slightly higher compared to the introductory exercise. This is likely due to the different design of the tasks: for the introduction exercise a part of the solution has already been given to the students.

The survey and the analysis of the models confirm also assumption 2, but the results require a more detailed explanation. The results of statement 3 and 17 show: Understanding the task and abstracting the actual problem was a challenge for half of the respondents. This was exactly what we intended in order to teach students to deal with open interdisciplinary problems. Slightly more than half of the respondents stated, that it was easy to solve the tasks based on the lecture (statement 7). The analysis of the models reflects precisely this result. Slightly more than half of the submissions shows good and very good results. Furthermore, the technical evaluation of the tasks confirms: all except 6 groups were able to apply key concepts of the lecture to solve the open interdisciplinary problems. However, the content-related evaluation differs from the technical evaluation. The results show: the tasks were asked in a way, that the students were basically able to abstract and model the actual problem, see the 16 good and outstanding submissions. But correctly solving open issues in terms of interdisciplinary contents, e.g. implementing physical laws, is also a challenge for the students – see the 14 unsatisfactorily content-related submissions. However, good and excellent content-related results were always accompanied by good technical results. We can conclude from this that a good understanding of the underlying theory is a prerequisite for a successful solution of the task, which proves that the tasks are well designed. Overall, the self-assessment of the respondents also confirms assumption 2: The application-oriented labs help students to abstract the actual problem of open interdisciplinary problems and to apply key concepts of the lecture to solve them. But the results also show, that solving the open application-oriented task, in particular the understanding of task, has not been easy for all students.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed the use of open application-oriented tasks in education to improve the comprehension of theoretical concepts and the competence to solve complex problems. For this purpose, we considered the course “Software Verification” at a German university of technology. The main challenge was teaching the ability to model systems from an interdisciplinary context at a level of abstraction that allows to successfully apply formal verification, one of the key concepts of the module software verification. We designed open application-oriented labs with an application context from medical technology to overcome this challenge. To evaluate the effect of the labs, we used a mixed-method approach of student questionnaires and an analysis of student-submitted lab reports. That confirmed our assumption that the open application-oriented labs help students to better comprehend the key concepts of the lecture as well as to be able to understand and abstract an open interdisciplinary problem and apply key concepts to solve it. But the results also confirmed that

some students have difficulties to work on open interdisciplinary issues. If we want to prepare students for professional life, then we need to integrate more teaching formats like research-based learning that potentially enable the acquisition of skills such as *complex and interdisciplinary problem solving*. The challenge is and remains to find the balance between challenging the better students and supporting the weaker students so that in the end all students acquire the competencies of understanding the subject-specific theories and learn to solve complex problems. Open application-oriented labs are one promising way to overcome the bottleneck in teaching *complex, interdisciplinary problem solving* and also to awaken the interest in the theory. But in the implementation, it must be ensured that the weaker students receive suitable support to also solve such tasks successfully. This point remains open and will be addressed in future work.

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